

PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN GEOGRAPHIC AREAS**Olimova Aziza Abdullaevna**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118805>**Abstract**

The article describes the practical importance of geographic sites, the method of organizing observation and practical work in geography classes.

Key words: geographical area, experimental lesson, practical training, students, observation, weather, sundial, weather vane, rock.

Today, our government pays special attention to the development of practical skills in the educational process, ensuring the harmony of theory and practice in lessons. Because, as a result of conducting education in connection with practice, the professional flexibility of graduates is facilitated.

Most of the practical work and observations in geography lessons are carried out on a specially equipped geography platform. In particular, here it is possible to systematically monitor the weather and the setting of the sun, to orientate in place, to carry out distance measurement, as well as to perform tasks related to the program of natural science and geography.

For the construction of the geography field, an open area of approximately 10m x 10m is selected so that it is not shaded by large trees and buildings. The area is leveled, sprinkled with sand and fenced around. It is preferable that the geography site is located next to the training site [1].

In order to conduct science classes, the following equipment must be available on the site:

Surveyor-wall. For this, every meter of the wrapping is used with one side painted with different paints. The height of the wall is -1 m. A path is dug along the measuring wall. It is used for the development of spatial imagination, including when passing the subject of "Spatial plan and map".

Height-measuring pole, height 10 m., each meter is alternately colored in two different colors. It serves to compare heights, as well as to develop spatial and measurement skills. A wind vane is installed at the end of the column [2].

Wind vane is an instrument for determining the direction of the wind. It can be made by students from tin or purchased from the store along with an anemometer to determine the wind strength.

A height meter is a wooden tool for measuring height. Using a height meter, students measure their own height and compare it to the height of other objects.

In this, the eyeball develops. A square meter is made of 1 m length of slats. It is placed on the platform and crushed bricks are placed in it. It gives a visual representation of the square meter [3].

Gnomon. An instrument that determines the height of the sun above the horizon. With the help of a gnomon, it is also possible to determine the directions of the sides of the horizon. For example, in the middle of the day, the shadow shows the direction to the north and is short, because the Sun is standing (at the zenith), in the morning the shadow is directed to the west, and in the evening the shadow is directed to the east [7]. In order to always know the direction to the north, the shadow of the gnomon is marked with oil paint or a piece of brick at midday.

A rhumb ring is used to make positional readings relative to the horizon. For this purpose, it is placed around the gnomon by inserting bricks or wood halfway into the ground. Circle - the initials of the names of the sides of the horizon are placed on the outer side of the ring [4]. According to the meridian line, north, opposite - south, on the right - east, on the left - west, and the intermediate sides between them - NE, NW, SW, SE are determined.

A sundial is a horizontal wooden circle of any size with an arrow in the middle. The number 12 is placed on the edge of the circle according to the gnomon (according to the shadow of the pillar, that is, the arrow pointing to the north at noon). The remaining numbers are placed at an equal distance from each other. Students of all grades can use the sundial. It is installed in the most open place to the south of the site.

Rain gauge. A simple bucket can serve as a rain gauge. It uses a ruler lowered into a bucket to determine the amount of rain. Can be measured using a beaker. For this, the indicator of the beaker in cubic centimeters is multiplied by 10 and divided by the level of the bottom of the bucket.

Snow gauge. The thickness of the snow cover is measured with a special ruler with corresponding lines.

A meteorological booth is used to store a thermometer that measures air temperature, a barometer that measures air pressure, a hygrometer that measures air humidity, and other instruments. The meteorological booth is installed at a height of about two meters in a place where there is no shadow on the geography site [5].

A box with sand is placed next to the work tables (4-5) and is used for students to create various relief forms.

Orientation corner serves to strengthen acquired knowledge, training and skills. It should be installed with its rings facing south on the day of cutting, and should

have slopes (steep and sloping), a pass and a model of a hill (of stones covered with turf) with a well-defined peak and base.

Equipment for studying the behavior of rocks and water includes an artificial water body, a model river, rocks and soil of the site. In order to study the work of running water, a water pipe is placed in the geography field. A barrier is placed in the path of the artificial flow of water to show the washing of the banks and the formation of the waterfall [6]. The success of work in the field of geography depends on their systematicity and constant supervision by the teacher.

The importance of field work. A school training ground is necessary for observation and experiments on agricultural plants. It is a one-of-a-kind outdoor laboratory where students deepen their knowledge of natural science, learn and develop plant care skills, and do hands-on work observing plant life and development. The field is a base for agricultural experiments and additional practical work of young naturalists: because plants studied in natural science classes are grown here.

Each student of primary school should grow a certain number of flowers, ornamental herbs, trees or vegetables during their studies. While choosing plants to grow, the teacher takes into account the complexity of their care, climate characteristics, ease-difficulty of the theoretical material related to the cultivation of these plants, etc. it is necessary to get

The school training ground should be located directly near the school, the ground should be flat, well-drained, and not shaded. It will definitely need to be wrapped around it. Let the school site be exemplary in terms of agrotechnics. He is adopted by a biology teacher. When organizing the playground, it is necessary to plan for a smaller room for training with students, for storing the playground and work tools.

Before the training, a work plan should be drawn up on the training ground: it should include the organization of the ground area of the field, the placement of crops, the size of the area occupied by them, the practical work, experiments and observations performed by the students in accordance with the training program; their implementation and procedure; It is necessary to reflect the deadlines, the experimental work of naturalists, the summer work of students, and the expected harvest. The plan should give a clear picture of the contents of the works to be carried out at the site this year and the measures to ensure their implementation. Methodology of work on the preschool playground by classes.

Work on the training ground can be divided into compulsory work carried out during class with the whole class, compulsory work done by students outside of

class (in the form of homework or summer assignments) and work of members of the young natural science club.

In the first grade, students get acquainted with trees, shrubs and herbs in autumn, with the variety and beauty of the shapes and colors of their leaves and flowers, with hand tools (hash, zambil) and methods of working with them.

In the spring, practical work is conducted with first graders on the training ground. They will learn the rules of planting seeds and their care, watering, planting, driving stakes. Older schoolchildren perform the work of soil cultivation, marza, and flowerbeds. First graders prepare the seeds for planting and plant them in the ground, take care of the plants.

In the 2nd grade, children get acquainted with the rules of labor safety and personal hygiene that must be followed during work on the training ground in the fall, the rules for collecting and storing seeds, prepare the classroom for tilling the soil in the fall, collect fallen leaves and branches, plant residues and garbage. they take out. The older students dig up the soil.

In the spring, students of the second grade prepare the seeds of ornamental and leguminous plants for sowing: for this, they select large and healthy seeds, freeze and collect them, sow the seeds in the soil, grow plants (carnations, marigolds, peas, beans, etc.). Then they level the marzas with a hoe, draw a line and make a ditch, sow the seeds in the ground and bury them in the same way, install a label, take care of the plants (water, soften the soil, plant the marzas, install support piles). Under the guidance of the teacher, children conduct an experiment of simultaneous planting of dry, warmed and harvested seeds (recording the emergence of grasses and the development of plants), and also conduct observations to determine the dependence of plant growth on external conditions (temperature, light, humidity).

Students of the 3rd grade get acquainted with the rules of labor safety and personal hygiene when working with a shovel and a shovel in the fall, collect seeds of plants grown in the field, clean the site from plant residues, apply fertilizers, turn the soil, and finish the work at the preschool educational-experimental site during the second grade. they prepare exhibits for the school exhibition.

In the spring, 3rd graders prepare the seeds of root crops (radish, beets, carrots) and annual flower ornamental plants (cosmeia, aster, itogiz, gorse) for planting. Seedling thickness to the yield of root crops: planting period to the yield of root crops and flowering time of ornamental plants; conduct experiments and observations to determine the effect of fertilizers on the yield of root crops and the growth and development of ornamental plants. They sow the seeds of

rhizomes and flower ornamental plants in the ground, make experiments and take care of the crops, irrigate and soften the land, make meadows and meadows, plant seedlings. In addition, 3rd graders prepare and plant cuttings of currants, grapes, pomegranates, and roses, take care of bruised plants.

Students of the 4th grade collect and count the harvest in the fall, get acquainted with the rules of their storage, collect seeds, cultivate the soil, prepare berries, bushes and fruit trees for the winter. In addition, children remove the old bark from the trunk and main stem of fruit trees, put soil around the trunk, add fertilizer to it, plant berries and decorative bushes.

In the spring, 4th graders check the fertility of vegetables and ornamental plants, grow seedlings of vegetables and ornamental plants (tomatoes, cabbage, sabbay, aromatic tobacco, etc.), take care of seedlings and transplant them, prepare the soil for spring planting in the collection area and in the flower garden in the first grade. and seedlings are prepared for planting, soften around the trunks of trees, sow seeds on the collection site and flower bed, and feed the green plants. In addition, children take care of perennial flower ornamental plants, multiply their bushes by dividing them, plant rooted seedlings in permanent places, fight against garden and lawn pests.

In general, in the field of modern geography, qualifications and skills are formed that allow to follow geographical laws and natural phenomena, and the harmony of theory and practice is ensured in the training sessions organized here.

New information obtained from observing nature through modern equipment is used in the educational process. Positively affects students' attitude to nature.

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